

The Influence Budget Planning, Cost Control, and Accounting Information Systems on Managerial Performance in LPD Negara District

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ABSTRACT

Managerial performance is the ability of managers to carry out management functions such as planning, controlling, organizing, and decision-making to achieve organizational goals. In village-based financial institutions such as the Village Credit Institution (LPD), managerial performance is a crucial factor in maintaining the sustainability and effectiveness of financial management. This study aims to analyze the factors influencing managerial performance in the LPD in Negara District by examining the influence of budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems on managerial performance. This study uses a quantitative approach. The population in this study were 70 LPD administrators in Negara District. The sampling method used was purposive sampling. The sample size in this study was 68 respondents who were LPD administrators who met the sample criteria. The data analysis technique used was multiple linear regression analysis. Based on the results of the data analysis, it can be concluded that budget planning has a positive effect on managerial performance, cost control has a positive effect on managerial performance, while accounting information systems have no effect on managerial performance in the LPD in Negara District.

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KEYWORDS: Managerial Performance, Budget Planning, Cost Control, Accounting Information Systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Managerial performance is a key factor determining a company's success in achieving its strategic goals. Recent research by Meiryani *et al.* (2022) demonstrates that managerial performance measures the efficiency and effectiveness with which a manager performs managerial tasks for Lembaga Perkreditan Desa (LPD), which play a strategic role in supporting the rural economy in Bali. As financial institutions based on Hindu customs and traditions, LPD have proven capable of providing financial services to low-income communities and small businesses (Kurniasari, 2021). The existence of LPD is becoming increasingly important in the context of inclusive economic development, particularly in the digital era, which demands adaptation and innovation in financial institution management.

Recent data shows that the performance of LPD in Bali faces significant challenges, particularly following the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to information from the Direktorat Jenderal Pajak (2022), LPD profits in Bali decreased by 27.3% year-on-year to IDR 398.63 billion, despite capital growth of 7% to IDR 4.47 trillion. This situation indicates pressure on LPD operational

efficiency and profitability, requiring serious attention in financial and managerial aspects.

On the other hand, total LPD assets across Bali also decreased from IDR 24.3 trillion in 2019 to IDR 23.6 trillion in 2020 (Sekretariat DPRD Provinsi Bali, 2021). This decline was not only caused by external factors such as the pandemic but also indicated weaknesses in the internal control and performance management systems of various LPD.

The LPD in Negara District, as part of the LPD ecosystem in Bali, faces similar challenges in maintaining and improving managerial performance. In this context, three fundamental aspects are crucial to evaluate: budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems. These three aspects interact to shape the effectiveness of managerial performance, which ultimately determines the sustainability and growth of LPD. However, the LPD in Negara District has different contextual characteristics than the southern part of Bali, which is dominated by the tourism sector, with a more heterogeneous economic structure that relies on MSMEs, local trade, and micro-scale services. This condition increases the complexity of financial management and requires LPD managers to be more adaptive in budget

planning, more disciplined in cost control, and more optimal in utilizing accounting information systems to support managerial decision-making.

This phenomenon indicates a performance gap in the implementation of the management system, which can impact managerial performance at the LPD in Negara District. Several contributing factors include weak coordination between divisions in the budget planning and cost control process, as well as limited investment in accounting information technology.

Budgeting planning is a fundamental management tool for directing company activities and optimally allocating resources. According to recent research by Sumarni & Mokodompit (2025), cost management planning is a crucial process in project management, involving defining how project costs will be managed throughout the project life cycle. The budget serves not only as a planning tool but also as a mechanism for coordination, communication, and performance evaluation, enabling management to strategically align organizational goals with operational activities. Research by Aziz & Fitriaty (2023), Mokodompit *et al.* (2022), Gultom *et al.* (2023), Suarmanayasa (2023), Pello *et al.* (2025), Fatimah (2024), Muzdalifa & Dalimunthe (2024), showed that budget planning has a positive effect on managerial performance. Meanwhile, research by Maulana *et al.* (2024), Juwita & Kusumanigrum (2019) showed that budget planning has no effect on managerial performance.

Cost control is a critical aspect of company operations, directly related to profitability and competitiveness. According to the Asana Team (2025), cost control involves identifying and reducing expenses to increase company profits, which can occur at the project or company-wide level. In the context of capital-intensive industries with complex cost structures, management's ability to control production costs, overhead costs, and other operational costs is a key determinant of company success. Research conducted by Telaumbanua & Munthe (2024) confirms that management accounting is related to providing accurate information for decision-making, planning, cost control, and performance evaluation. Research by Nathanael & Suriyanti (2025), Assiddiqi *et al.* (2024), Wulandari (2020), indicates that cost control has a positive effect on managerial performance. Meanwhile, research by Khasanah *et al.* (2024) indicates that cost control has no effect on managerial performance.

Accounting Information Systems (AIS) have become the backbone of managerial decision-making in the digital era. An integrated AIS is capable of providing accurate, relevant, and timely real-time information to support planning, control, and performance evaluation. According to Romney & Steinbart (2021), the quality of accounting information systems significantly influences the effectiveness of managerial decision-making and organizational performance. Research by Khasanah *et al.* (2024), Dewi *et al.* (2025),

Ganung *et al.* (2025), Muzdalifa & Dalimunthe (2024), indicates that accounting information systems have a positive effect on managerial performance. Meanwhile, research by Prasetyo *et al.* (2024), Nofiana *et al.* (2023), Rahmawati *et al.* (2022), Ariani *et al.* (2024) indicates that accounting information systems have no effect on managerial performance.

The theoretical basis of this research is based on Contingency Theory, which states that the effectiveness of a management control system depends on situational factors such as technology, environment, and organizational structure. This theory is highly relevant considering the unique characteristics of LPDs as customary-based institutions with their own managerial complexities. Management Control System Theory explains how organizations use integrated mechanisms to direct behavior in achieving strategic goals, while Information System Theory emphasizes the role of technology in supporting the effectiveness of organizational control.

An empirical study of the quality of accounting information at LPDs in South Denpasar District shows that information technology and internal control significantly influence the quality of accounting information systems (Pramesti *et al.* 2022). This finding indicates the importance of technology integration in LPD accounting systems to improve the accuracy and relevance of the information produced.

Research by Supratinigrum & Lukas (2021) on garment companies demonstrated that management accounting information systems and management control systems positively impact managerial performance, with information technology acting as a moderating variable. These findings provide a strong theoretical basis for exploring similar relationships in the context of LPDs. However, specific research integrating these three aspects within the context of LPDs in Negara District is still limited. This research gap is crucial to fill, given the unique characteristics of LPDs as customary-based financial institutions with their own complexities in managerial management.

Previous studies on the relationship between budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems with managerial performance have been conducted by various researchers. However, there are still inconsistencies in research gaps and limited generalizability of findings, particularly in the context of LPDs. Research by Merchant & Van der Stede (2017), showed a significant positive effect, while a study by Hidayat (2020) produced mixed results.

Furthermore, there are still limitations in research that integrates all three variables simultaneously within a single research model. Most previous studies examine the influence of variables partially or only combine two variables, thus failing to provide a comprehensive understanding of the synergistic effects of integrating budget planning, cost

control, and accounting information systems on managerial performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

A. Contingency Theory

Contingency theory is a fundamental theoretical foundation for understanding how management control systems operate in different organizational contexts. It was first developed by Fiedler (1964) and later expanded by various researchers in the context of management accounting. According to Otley (2016), contingency theory states that there is no universally optimal management control system for all organizations; rather, the effectiveness of such a system depends on the situational factors or contingencies faced by the organization. In the context of LPDs, contingency theory is highly relevant because these institutions have unique characteristics as customary-based financial institutions operating within a specific cultural and regulatory environment. Contingency factors that influence the effectiveness of management control systems include organizational size, information technology, environmental uncertainty, and organizational strategy (Chenhall, 2003). The application of contingency theory in this study helps explain how budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems should be adapted to the specific characteristics of LPDs in Negara District to achieve optimal managerial performance.

B. Stewardship Theory

Stewardship theory is a perspective that emphasizes collective behavior and organizational goal orientation. According to Davis et al. (1997), this theory assumes that managers as stewards are intrinsically motivated to act in the best interests of the organization, rather than their own personal interests. In the context of LPDs, which are based on customs and strong communal values, stewardship theory is highly relevant. Stewardship theory explains that LPD managers, who are often members of the local indigenous community, tend to have a moral and psychological commitment to managing organizational resources responsibly. Donaldson & Davis (1991) argue that in situations where there is value alignment between managers and the organization, a stewardship approach will be more effective than strict control mechanisms. In the context of this research, stewardship theory helps explain how budget planning and cost control systems can be designed to empower LPD managers as responsible stewards.

C. Budget Planning on Managerial Performance

This hypothesis is based on Contingency Theory, which explains that participatory budget planning involving various stakeholders will be more effective in improving managerial performance (Otley, 2016). In the context of LPDs, which have a customary-based organizational structure with the involvement of traditional village

administrators, a participatory approach to budget planning is highly relevant to ensuring alignment between organizational goals and community interests.

Stewardship theory reinforces that LPD managers who have intrinsic commitment will be more motivated when given the opportunity to participate in budget planning (Davis et al. 1997). As part of the traditional village community, LPD managers have strong moral and social ties to the organization, so their participation in the budgeting process not only increases their sense of ownership but also accountability in achieving targets (Anthony & Govindarajan, 2007).

Empirical evidence from Prasmangi et al. (2025) shows that adequate budgetary participation improves managers' discipline and understanding of the budget, which significantly improves managerial performance. Research by Aziz & Fitriaty (2023) also proves that budgetary participation improves managerial performance by promoting goal clarity and commitment. In the context of the LPD in Negara District, budget planning involving managers will improve their understanding of financial and operational targets, enabling them to carry out managerial functions such as planning, coordination, and evaluation more effectively. Based on this, the first hypothesis is:

H1: Budget planning has a positive effect on managerial performance.

D. Cost Control on Managerial Performance

This hypothesis is based on Contingency Theory, which explains that in the microfinance services industry with relatively thin profit margins, cost control is a critical factor for organizational sustainability (Chenhall, 2003). LPDs operate in a competitive environment with the presence of various formal financial institutions and fintech, so the ability to control operational costs is a crucial determinant in maintaining competitiveness and profitability.

Stewardship theory emphasizes that sound cost control assists managers in carrying out their responsibilities to manage organizational resources efficiently (Donaldson & Davis, 1991). As stewards responsible to the traditional village and its community, LPD managers have a moral obligation to ensure that every rupiah spent adds value to the organization and the community they serve. Effective cost control contributes significantly to managerial performance through several mechanisms: A sound cost control system provides information on variances between actual and budgeted costs, enabling managers to identify inefficiencies and take proactive corrective action (Garrison et al. 2020).

Empirical evidence from Adegbie et al. (2020), Nathanael & Suriyanti (2025), Assiddiqi et al. (2024), shows that cost control techniques have a significant impact on organizational performance. These studies found that organizations implementing strict cost control systems experienced significant increases in profitability and

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operational efficiency. In the context of the LPD in Negara District, effective cost control will enable managers to allocate resources optimally, reduce waste, and improve overall managerial performance. Based on this explanation, the second hypothesis is:

H2: Cost control has a positive effect on managerial performance.

E. Accounting Information Systems on Managerial Performance

An Accounting Information System (AIS) is a system that functions to collect, record, process, and present financial information used in the decision-making process. Contingency Theory explains that the effectiveness of an organizational system is not universal, but depends on the suitability of the system to the conditions and environment of the organization. In this context, an effective Accounting Information System (AIS) will provide optimal contributions to managerial performance if it is aligned with the needs of the organization, job characteristics, and environmental conditions of the LPD (Fiedler, 1964; Otley, 2016).

Meanwhile, Stewardship Theory explains that managers are viewed as trustworthy parties (stewards) who are oriented towards achieving organizational goals (Davis et al. 1997). In the context of LPD, managers who are committed to the organization will utilize the Accounting Information System optimally to support goal achievement, increase efficiency, and maintain accountability for financial management. DeLone & McLean (2003) information systems success model emphasizes that system quality, information quality, and service quality influence net benefits for the organization.

Empirical research supports a positive relationship between AIS and managerial performance. Fitrius et al. (2018), found that management accounting information systems (AMS) have a positive and significant impact on managerial performance, with an effective AIS improving the quality of decision-making and inter-unit coordination. Sanad (2024) showed that AIS quality significantly influences decision-making success and overall organizational performance. Pramesti et al. (2022) research on LPDs in South Denpasar District showed that information technology and internal control significantly influence the quality of accounting information systems, which ultimately impacts managerial effectiveness. Based on this explanation, the third hypothesis is:

H3: Accounting information systems have a positive effect on managerial performance.

F. Research Model

This study develops a conceptual framework that describes the relationship between budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems as independent variables with managerial performance as the dependent

variable in the context of LPD Negara District. The research model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Model

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted across all LPDs in Negara District. This research was conducted across all LPDs in Negara District because it aligns with the research object and facilitates the researcher in obtaining relevant data to support the research process. The object and population in this study were all 70 LPD administrators from 8 LPDs in Negara District. The sampling method used was purposive sampling, with a total of 68 observations. This study used a questionnaire for data collection with a five-point Likert scale and distributed via Google Form. The data analysis technique used was multiple linear regression analysis. This study used managerial performance as the dependent variable. The independent variables were budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems.

The indicators and question items for each variable are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Research Instruments

Variables	Indicator
Managerial Performance (Y)	1. Planning, 2. Investigating, 3. Coordinating, 4. Evaluating, 5. Supervising, 6. Staffing, 7. Negotiating, 8. Representing
Budget Planning (X1)	1. Participation in budget preparation 2. Clarity of budget targets 3. Alignment of budget with organizational strategy 4. Budget flexibility 5. Budget feedback 6. Budget evaluation
Cost Control (X2)	1. Cost variance analysis 2. Setting cost standards

Garrison <i>et al.</i> (2020), Drury (2018)		3. Monitoring operational costs	
		4. Efficient use of resources	
		5. Corrective action on cost deviations	
		6. Timely cost reporting	
		Accounting Information System (X3)	1. System quality (reliability and ease of use)
		Romney & Steinbart (2021), DeLone & McLean (2003)	2. Information quality (accuracy, relevance, completeness, timeliness)
	3. Service quality (technical support and training)		
	4. System integration		
	5. Data security		
	6. Information accessibility		

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results

A. Descriptive Statistical Test

Table 2. Results of Descriptive Statistical Test

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
X1	68	11,00	20,00	18,2353	1,94796
X2	68	13,00	20,00	17,3676	1,54441
X3	68	11,00	20,00	17,3235	1,71422
Y	68	4,00	20,00	17,3529	2,45414

Source: Processed data (2026)

Descriptive statistics show that the budget planning variable (X₁) has an average value of 18.23 with an average score of 4.56 which is included in the “Completely Agree” category, thus indicating that budget planning at the LPD of Negara District is classified as very good. The cost control variable (X₂) has an average value of 17.36 with an average score of 4.34 which is included in the “Agree” category, indicating that cost control at the LPD is classified as good. Furthermore, the accounting information system variable (X₃) has an average value of 17.32 with an average score of 4.33 which is also included in the “Agree” category, thus indicating that the accounting information system at the LPD is in the good category. Meanwhile, the managerial performance variable (Y) has an average value of 17.35 with an average score of 4.34 which is included in the “Agree” category, indicating that managerial performance at the LPD of Negara District is classified as good even though there is a slightly higher variation in respondents' answers compared to other variables.

Validity test results showed that all statement items had Pearson Correlation values greater than 0,3, thus being

declared valid. Meanwhile, reliability test results showed a Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0,7, thus declaring the research instrument reliable. Hypothesis testing was conducted using multiple linear regression analysis, which had previously been validated based on classical assumptions. The normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed a significance value of 0.053, indicating a normal data distribution. The multicollinearity test showed a tolerance value greater than 0.10 and a variance inflation factor less than 10, indicating the absence of multicollinearity. This regression model also showed no signs of heteroscedasticity.

B. Hypothesis Test (t-test)

Table 3. Results of the t-test

Variable.	Coef.	t-Statistic.	Sig.	Prediction
X1	0,764	5,018	0,001	H1(+)
X2	0,338	2,049	0,045	H2(+)
X3	0,010	0,061	0,952	H3
Constant	-2,622	-1,059	0,294	
Adjusted R-Square	0,546			
Probability (F-statistic)	27,888		0,001	
N	86			

** Sig. on level 0,05 (p<0,05)

Source: Processed data (2026)

The model fit test yielded an adjusted R-squared value of 0.546, indicating that budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems variables only explain 54.6% of managerial performance. The remaining 45.4% is attributed to other variables outside the scope of this research model. The F-value is 27.888 with a significance level of 0.001 < 0.05. This indicates that budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems simultaneously influence managerial performance.

The budget planning test showed a significance value of 0.001, indicating that the results supported H1. The cost control test showed a significance value of 0.045, thus supporting H2. Meanwhile, the accounting information system test showed a significance value of 0.952, indicating that the results did not support H3.

Discussions

A. The Influence of Budget Planning on Managerial Performance

The first hypothesis states that budget planning has a positive effect on managerial performance. The budget planning variable has a regression coefficient of 0.764 and a significance value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05. The results of the study indicate that budget planning has a positive effect on managerial performance at the LPD in Negara District, thus H1 is accepted. These results indicate

that better budget planning will improve managerial performance.

Based on Contingency Theory, an organization's effectiveness is influenced by the alignment of its management system with the conditions and needs of its environment (Fiedler, 1964). In this context, budget planning is an important managerial tool to help organizations set targets, allocate resources, and coordinate operational activities effectively (Gultom et al. 2023). Good budget planning provides clear guidelines for management in carrying out tasks and making decisions, thereby improving managerial performance. Furthermore, Stewardship Theory explains that managers, as stewards, strive to work optimally to achieve organizational goals (Davis et al. 1997). Managerial involvement in the budget preparation process can increase a sense of responsibility and commitment to achieving organizational targets (Suarmanayasa, 2023). With clear, measurable budget planning aligned with LPD objectives, managers will find it easier to monitor, evaluate, and make decisions effectively. This condition encourages improved managerial performance because managers have a more structured and planned work direction (Aziz & Fitriaty, 2023). Systematic budget planning can assist management in developing work plans, controlling operational activities, and evaluating the achievement of organizational goals (Mokodompit et al. 2022). Therefore, the better the budget planning implemented at the LPD in Negara District, the higher the resulting managerial performance (Muzdalifa & Dalimunthe, 2024).

The results of this study are in line with those of Aziz & Fitriaty (2023), Mokodompit et al. (2022), Gultom et al. (2023), Suarmanayasa (2023), Pello et al. (2025), Fatimah (2024), Muzdalifa & Dalimunthe (2024), Safariah & Hodijah (2022), Mayasari et al. (2023), which show that budget planning has a positive effect on managerial performance. However, these results are not in line with those of Maulana et al. (2024), Juwita & Kusumanigrum (2019), Burokhman (2017), which show that budget planning has no effect on managerial performance.

B. The Influence of Cost Control on Managerial Performance

The second hypothesis states that cost control has a positive effect on managerial performance. The cost control variable has a regression coefficient of 0.338 and a significance value of 0.045, which is less than 0.05. The results of the study indicate that cost control has a positive effect on managerial performance at the LPD in Negara District, thus H2 is accepted. These results indicate that better cost control implementation will improve managerial performance.

Based on Contingency Theory, organizations require a control system that is appropriate to environmental

conditions and organizational needs so that goals can be achieved effectively (Fiedler, 1964). Cost control is a form of management control system that functions to ensure the use of resources is carried out efficiently and in accordance with the established budget. With good cost control, management can monitor operational expenses, identify cost deviations, and take corrective actions in a timely manner, thereby supporting improved managerial performance (Nathanael & Suriyanti, 2025). Stewardship Theory also explains that managers have a responsibility to act in the interests of the organization (Davis et al. 1997). In this case, effective cost control reflects management's efforts to maintain operational efficiency and maximize the achievement of organizational goals. Managers who are able to control costs well will more easily allocate resources optimally, reduce waste, and increase the effectiveness of decision-making (Nathanael & Suriyanti, 2025). These conditions will have a positive impact on improving managerial performance. Regular cost analysis, setting cost standards, monitoring operational costs, and presenting timely cost reports can assist management in carrying out oversight and decision-making functions more effectively (Assiddiqi et al. 2024). Therefore, the better the cost control implemented at the Negara District LPD, the higher the resulting managerial performance.

The results of this study align with those of Nathanael & Suriyanti (2025), Assiddiqi et al. (2024), Wulandari (2020), which stated that cost control has a positive effect on managerial performance. However, these results are inconsistent with the research of Khasanah et al. (2024), which stated that cost control has no effect on managerial performance.

C. The Influence of Accounting Information Systems on Managerial Performance

The third hypothesis states that the accounting information system has a positive effect on managerial performance. The accounting information system variable has a regression coefficient of 0.010 and a significance value of 0.952, which is greater than 0.05. The results indicate that the accounting information system does not affect managerial performance at the LPD in Negara District, thus H3 is rejected. This means that the accounting information system does not affect managerial performance.

Based on Contingency Theory, the effectiveness of accounting information system implementation is influenced by the suitability of the system used with the conditions and needs of the organization (Fiedler, 1964). Theoretically, a good accounting information system should be able to provide accurate, relevant, and timely information to support managerial decision-making. However, the results of this study indicate that accounting information systems have no effect on managerial performance (Prasetyo et al. 2024). This indicates that LPD management has not fully utilized

accounting information systems as a primary factor in improving managerial performance. Based on Stewardship Theory, managers as stewards will strive to achieve organizational goals by optimally utilizing available resources (Davis et al. 1997). However, managerial performance is not only influenced by the existence of accounting information systems, but also by individual abilities, work experience, organizational communication, and the effectiveness of direct decision-making. In practice, managers in LPDs likely rely more on experience, coordination, and direct supervision than on the use of accounting information systems in carrying out managerial activities (Ariani et al. 2024). Furthermore, the existing accounting information system may only be used as an administrative and reporting tool, thus not having a significant impact on improving managerial performance (Rahmawati et al. 2022). Therefore, the level of accounting information system implementation does not determine the level of managerial performance at the LPD in Negara District.

The results of this study are consistent with those of Prasetyo et al. (2024), Nofiana et al. (2023), Rahmawati et al. (2022), Ariani et al. (2024), which showed that accounting information systems had no effect on managerial performance. However, the results of this study are inconsistent with those of Khasanah et al. (2024), Dewi et al. (2025), Ganung et al. (2025), Muzdalifa & Dalimunthe (2024), which showed that accounting information systems had a positive effect on managerial performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to analyze the factors influencing managerial performance at the LPD (Lembaga Perusahaan Daerah Daerah Istimewa Kecamatan Negara) by examining the influence of budget planning, cost control, and accounting information systems on managerial performance. The study sample consisted of 68 respondents, LPD administrators who met the research criteria, namely having worked for at least one year and being actively involved in the managerial process. Based on the analysis and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Budget planning has a positive effect on managerial performance. This means that the better the budget planning, the higher the managerial performance.
2. Cost control has a positive effect on managerial performance. This means that the better the cost control implemented, the higher the managerial performance.
3. The accounting information system has no effect on managerial performance. This means that the better the accounting information system is, the better it is not a determining factor in improving managerial performance.

LIMITATION

This study has several limitations. It was conducted only on LPDs in Negara District, so the results cannot be generalized to LPDs in other regions or financial institutions with different characteristics. Furthermore, accounting information systems had no effect on managerial performance, suggesting that other factors that may mediate or moderate this relationship have not been examined.

SUGGESTION

Future research could broaden the scope by involving a broader range of subjects to improve the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, further research could include other variables such as human resource competency, the effectiveness of information technology use, organizational culture, information quality, and internal control systems, which are thought to influence managerial performance.

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